

The Vesica Piscis (Mandorla) and the Geometry of the Square Roots

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Politecnico di Torino

Here we shortly discuss the symmetric lens of the 2-dimensional geometry which is known as the "vesica piscis". In art and architecture, this lens is usually known as the "mandorla", which in Italian means almond. Previously, we have investigated some properties of its geometric form, related to the square root of 3. Now, we will show how it is possible to find the other square roots from this lens.

Torino, 25 November 2020. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4290813

A lens, in 2-dimensional geometry, is a region bounded by two circular arcs joined to each other at their endpoints. If we want to have a convex lens, both arcs must bow outwards the region. This geometric shape can be obtained by means of the intersection of two circles. In the case that the two arcs have the radius, we have a symmetric lens, otherwise an asymmetric lens.

In fact, a symmetric lens has obtained a wide popularity, due to the fact that it is a symbol of sacred geometry: it is the "vesica piscis" (from Latin, the "fish bladder" [1]). In this case, the lens is formed by arcs of two circles whose centres each lie on the opposite arc. The arcs meet at angles of 120° at their endpoints.

Actually, lenses are very old geometric forms, of which we find a discussion in the Euclid's geometry: Book III, Proposition 5: If two circles cut one another, they will not have the same centre. The Euclid's words are available at <https://www.claymath.org/library/historical/euclid/files/elem.3.5.html>

Screenshot from the above mentioned link.

And here what Euclid told. "If two circles cut one another, they will not have the same centre. For let the circles ABC, CDG cut one another at the points B, C; I say that they will not have the same centre. For, if possible, let it be E; let EC be joined, and let EFG be drawn through at random. Then, since the point E is the centre of the circle ABC, EC is equal to EF, Again, since the point E is the centre of the circle CDG, EC is equal to EG. But EC was proved equal to EF also; therefore EF is also equal to EG, the less to the greater: which is impossible. Therefore the point E is not the centre of the circles ABC, CDG".

Euclid did not use the term "vesica piscis". The origin of this term requires a detailed investigation, that we will make in a future work. In visual arts, the vesica piscis is usually known as the Mandorla, which in Italian means almond. The "mandorla" is a frame that surrounds the totality of an iconographic figure. Then we can find a mandorla often surrounding the images of Jesus Christ and the Virgin Mary in traditional Christian iconography [2]. It is commonly used to frame the figure of Christ in Majesty in early medieval Romanesque and Byzantine art. The lens is also the shape generally used for the mediaeval ecclesiastical seals, whereas the secular seals generally being round.

The lens of the vesica piscis, besides being used in arts, is a form of architecture [3]. It was used even to create the "ovato tondo" of the St. Peter's Square in Rome [4]. Actually, the vesica piscis was recommended by Sebastiano Serlio (1475-c.1554), the Italian Mannerist architect that helped canonize the classical orders of architecture, for the construction of this "ovato" [5]. The vesica piscis is the simplest and quickest manner to construct oval spaces.

The Vesica Piscis (Mandorla) in the Bernini's Ovato of Saint Peter's Square [4]

In [6], we have investigated some properties of the geometric form. In it we can find the square root of 3. Now, can we find other square roots in the vesica piscis? This is a question that we can propose as exercises in geometry.

And here some possible exercises.

1) The Vesica Piscis is a lens formed by the intersection of two circles with the same radius. The intersecting happens in such a way that the centre of each circle lies on the circumference of the other. Draw the two circles having this property. Consider the length of the radius equal to 1. Find in the figure the segments having the following lengths: $\sqrt{1}$, $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{3}$, $\sqrt{4}$, $\sqrt{5}$. First, let us note that it means to search 1 , $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{3}$, 2 , $\sqrt{5}$.

All we have to do is to search for right triangles and use the Pythagorean theorem.

2) Starting from the square root of 2, find square root of 8 and square root of 10.

3) Is it existing another manner to find the square root of 10?

In fact, $\sqrt{10} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{5})^2 + (\sqrt{5})^2} = \sqrt{2 \cdot 5}$ but also $\sqrt{10} = \sqrt{1^2 + 3^2}$.

4) Where we can find square root of 7? (suggestion, use $\sqrt{3}$).

As we have seen, we can find several other square roots.

5) Search for a square root of 6.

Let us check the result. In the figure we can see that it must be less than 2.5. And in fact, $\sqrt{6}=2.449\dots$.

6) So we have seen where we can find $\sqrt{1}, \sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}, \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{5}, \sqrt{6}$ and also, if we consider $3 = \sqrt{9}$, the following roots $\sqrt{7}, \sqrt{8}, \sqrt{9}, \sqrt{10}$. However where is the square root of 11?

That is, we can use the same trick as we made in case of the square root of 6.

It is easy to imagine different manners, based on the vesica piscis, to show the geometry of the square roots. Moreover, besides these problems, we can also use the mandorla to create other geometric figures, such as the hexagon in the flower of life.

The hexagon in the flower of life [7].

References

- [1] Pedoe, D. *Circles: A Mathematical View*, rev. ed. Washington, DC: Math. Assoc. Amer., 1995.
- [2] Liungman, Carl G. (1991). *Dictionary of Symbols*. W.W. Norton. p. 287. ISBN 0-393-31236-4.
- [3] Barrallo, J., González-Quintial, F. & Sánchez-Beitia, S. An Introduction to the Vesica Piscis, the Reuleaux Triangle and Related Geometric Constructions in Modern Architecture. *Nexus Netw J* 17, 671–684 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00004-015-0253-9>
- [4] Sparavigna, A.C. (2015). Light and Shadows in Bernini's Oval of Saint Peters Square, PHILICA.COM, Article number 540. Available <https://iris.polito.it/retrieve/handle/11583/2721714/223467>
- [5] Rosin, P. L. (2001). On Serlio's constructions of ovals. *The Mathematical Intelligencer*, 23(1), 58-69. DOI: 10.1007/bf03024523
- [6] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina, & Baldi, Mauro Maria. (2016). A Mathematical Study of a Symbol: The Vesica Piscis of Sacred Geometry. PHILICA, (560). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4288186>
- [7] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina and Baldi, Mauro Maria, Flower of Life, Six-Fold Symmetry and Honeycomb Packing of Circles in the Mycenaean Geometry (March 29, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2756099> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2756099>